

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES OF LEARNING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article highlights several ways to learn English effectively and some of the innovative learning technologies in language learning as well.

Keywords: Language, English, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

Today, foreign language skills are becoming an integral part of vocational education. Due to the high level of cooperation with foreign partners in various fields, the demand for language learning is high. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important part of vocational education. Such knowledge is first acquired by people in schools, colleges, high schools, and later in institutes, training courses, or by familiarizing themselves with basic information sets that help them learn a foreign language independently.

Today, the main focus is on the student, his personality and his unique inner world. Therefore, the main task of a modern teacher is to choose effective methods and forms of language teaching. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been on the rise. It is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the learning process. The main purpose of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture for language learners, to teach them to master for the foreign languages.

The main task of the language teachers is to create conditions for each learner to practice the language, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate their activism and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the student's cognitive activity in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies such as collaborative learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, internet resources help to implement a person-centered approach in the learning process. Forms of working with excellent language teaching programs in foreign language classes include: increasing vocabulary; practice correct pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monopolistic speech; write teaching; develop grammatical phenomena.

One of the innovative ways to teach foreign languages to learners is to use new innovative methods using the internet in these lessons, to develop reading skills and competencies using global networking materials; improving students' writing skills; replenish students' vocabulary; to motivate students to learn a foreign language. In addition, the method aims to broaden the horizons of language learners, exploring the possibilities of internet technology to establish and maintain business relationships and connections with peers in foreign-speaking countries. Students can take part in online tests, quizzes, competitions, Olympiads, correspondence with their peers in other countries, conversations, video conferences, etc.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using internet resources is to create interactions in this lesson, which is usually in the methodology called interactivity. Interactivity is through the means of speech is to unite, coordinate, and complement the communicative goal and the resulting effort. The Internet helps to develop speaking skills and abilities in foreign language teaching, and the use of innovative methods in teaching vocabulary and grammar ensures a sincere interest in the language and increases efficiency. Interactivity not only creates real-life situations, but also forces students to respond appropriately to them in a foreign language.

As one of the innovative methods, organizing speeches with native speakers through Skype, Facebook and other social networks and organizing debates on these

networks can greatly contribute to the development of language learners' comprehension and speaking skills. In addition, the quizizz.com platform, which is available on the internet, can be of great help to language learners. In this case, the teacher prepares grammatical, lexical questions about the language and places them on the platform, and students enter the platform using their smartphones and answer the questions. The platform automatically scores for each correct answer and shows that scored how many points at the end of the game. This, in turn, creates a sense of competition among students using innovative interactive methods in language teaching. Students who score high at the end of the game will be encouraged by the teacher.

It is advisable to teach grammar to students studying foreign languages in depth. Based on the grammar rules, students will be given exercises and tests to test their knowledge. Language learning software on computers and phones is a great way to teach a language. Examples of such programs are: Talk (English speaking practice), Daily English, Learn English (English master), How to speak real English. These programs are designed to include reading, listening, and test sections. Recording new words on a phone dictaphone is another great way to repeat listening in your spare time. In addition, showing more English subtitles and cartoons is an effective way to teach the language.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the introduction of information technology in education significantly diversifies the process of information perception and processing. Thanks to computers, the Internet, and multimedia, it provides students with a unique opportunity to master large amounts of data with subsequent analysis and sorting. The motivational foundations of educational activities are also significantly expanded. With the use of multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, television, conduct interviews and teleconferences. All this allows learners to learn the language effectively.

REFERENCES

1. Johnson, K. E. The Sociocultural Turn and Its Challenges for Second Language Teacher Education. // TESOL Quarterly., – London., 2006.
2. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. – London., 2001.
3. Kevin D. Besnoy, Lane W. Clarke, High-Tech Teaching Success! A Stepby-Step Guide to Using Innovative Technology in Your Classroom, Prufrock Press, Inc. October 1, 2009
4. Lynne T. Diaz-Rico, Teaching English Learners: Strategies and Methods Marlene D. LeFever, Creative Teaching Methods, Cook Ministry Resources; March 1, 1997
5. internet resources